

The Impact of Mother Tongue Influence of Tribal Students at Graduation Level: An Experimental Study

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Abstract:

Language is a method of communicating ideas, thoughts, and desires by means of sounds for psychological survival. English acts as a second language, even though, it is not our mother tongue; it has become a Global language. The aim of teaching English is not to imitate the native speakers or to develop the British or American accents. The aim of this article is to discuss the mother tongue influence in speaking English amongst Tribal community and how one can overcome some of the problems come across by Tribal learner of English. Initially, when we start speaking in a second language, like English, we utilize sounds from our native tongue. Consequently, mother tongue influence (MTI) exists in everyone. First of all, with increasing exposure to speakers of the second language, speaking practice, and error correction, you gradually learn to substitute the sounds of your mother tongue with those of the English language. One such is the "z" sound, which appears frequently at the end of English words but not at their beginnings.

Keywords: Mother tongue, global, corporate culture, English communication.

Introduction:

Language plays a significant role in education and the overall development of individuals. For tribal students, who often come from diverse linguistic backgrounds, the choice of language for instruction at the graduation level becomes crucial. This article presents an experimental study that examines the influence of the mother tongue on the academic performance and overall well-being of tribal students at the graduation level. The study aims

to shed light on the importance of utilizing the mother tongue in education and its effects on the academic success of tribal students.

What is mother tongue?

Since the first population census was carried out in the 19th century, there has been a continuous effort in India to define the term "mother tongue." From "language spoken by the individual from the cradle" in 1881 to "parent language" in 1901 to "language ordinarily used" in 1921, the Census of India's definition of "mother tongue" has changed (Pattanayak quoted in Ladousa 2010). When there are more than 10,000 speakers, the term "language" is used in the 2011 Census. The NEP lacks adequate definitions and interchangeably refers to "mother tongue," "home language," "local language," and "regional language." This brings up the initial query: According to Ladousa (2010), 602, is a child's "mother tongue" the language they learnt first, the language they are most familiar with, the language they use the most, or the language of the state or country they live in? State governments make decisions on issues pertaining to education, even though federal policies can direct or affect how the educational system operates in every state. First introduced in 1956, the Three-Language Formula (TLF) mandated that schools teach a student's "mother tongue" or regional language for ten years, followed by six years of official language instruction (either English or Hindi), and three years of instruction in a third modern Indian or foreign language. This resulted in opposition to the advancement of Hindi as the "national" language of India, particularly in the southern states. In an attempt to offer a slightly different solution, NEP 2020 suggests that while three languages must still be taught in schools, at least two of them must be "native" to India. Naturally, the 22 languages listed in the Eighth Schedule of the Indian Constitution are the only ones available to you. These numbers do not include the 121 languages, 1369 "rationalized mother tongues," and more than 19,500 unidentified mother tongues that are spoken by different populations all over the nation (Press Trust of India 2018).

Simultaneously, the question of the medium of instruction has been scrutinized for decades. This culminated in the Central Board of Secondary Education (CBSE) 2005 National Curriculum Framework, which suggested teaching in the student's "mother tongue" until Class 5, almost as a forerunner to the NEP. As long as possible, the new policy encourages schools to carry on teaching in the mother tongue through Class 5. Additionally, it recommends that teachers, regardless of whether it is the official language of instruction, use their students' "home language" in casual classroom interactions to help students of all

linguistic backgrounds feel included in class discussions. Additionally, they have recommended the creation of the Indian Institute of Translation and Interpretation (IITI) in order to translate and create excellent educational resources in a variety of Indian languages.

The Importance of Mother Tongue in Education

A student's mother tongue is the language that they acquire first and use in their daily lives. It serves as the foundation for cognition, identity, and cultural preservation. Integrating the mother tongue in the education system has numerous benefits.

Comprehension and Conceptual Understanding

Research shows that utilizing the mother tongue in instruction helps students better understand and internalize complex concepts. A study conducted by Thomas and Collier (2002) found that students who were instructed in their mother tongue outperformed those who were taught in a second language. The students who learned in their mother tongue had better academic achievement, higher cognitive abilities, and stronger critical thinking skills.

When students are educated in their mother tongue, it promotes cognitive and emotional development. Mother tongue instruction facilitates effective communication and expression of thoughts and emotions, allowing students to fully engage in the learning process. This positively impacts their self-esteem, motivation, and overall well-being.

A study by Patrinos and Velez (1996) demonstrated that mother tongue education positively affected students' self-confidence and motivation. Students who learned in their mother tongue had higher attendance rates, better behaviour, and improved relationships with teachers and peers. For tribal students, incorporating the mother tongue in education is crucial for preserving their cultural identity. Language is deeply intertwined with culture, and when students learn in their mother tongue, they maintain a strong connection with their heritage and community. This fosters a sense of pride, belonging, and cultural continuity.

A study conducted by Zubeida (2010) emphasized the significance of mother tongue education for tribal students. The research highlighted that incorporating the mother tongue improved students' self-perception, cultural awareness, and pride in their identity.

English in the Current Educational Framework:

English is required in the current educational system starting with the first standard. However, it is notable that primary school teachers do not provide their students with the fundamental scientific understanding of English. It is well known that students in English-medium schools are capable of handling the material quite well, but what about those in other

languages? English is now taught starting in first grade in an effort to improve our children's social standing and employment prospects. It is widely recognized, nevertheless, that the entire process of teaching and learning, from undergraduate to graduate school and even beyond, is ineffective at providing students with the necessary language skills. The majority of pupils complete their education in their native tongue. Even though, they receive excellent grades in both English and core subjects, they still harbour an unidentified fear of the language.

It is tragic that the students in the rural area lack communication skills and English language proficiency. Compared to undergraduate students from rural areas, students from urban and semi-urban areas are proficient enough to gain a significant command over the English language. They are less conversant in the language and have less exposure to it. They continue to be completely devoid of the right instruction, environment, situation, and direction. As a result, they don't care for this language. They think the teaching style is tedious and onerous, so they avoid going to the classes.

Problem with Mother Tongue:

Dr. G. Rajgopal ESL, Hyderabad, discovered that having knowledge of one's mother tongue is actually a beneficial resource and not a barrier that a teacher of a second language such as English teacher can use in their teaching activities. The process of learning English benefits from having an understanding of one's mother tongue and its applications.

The majority of students finish their education in Telugu, the local language of this region, which is not their mother tongue. Their medium of instruction is Telugu, Bilingual or translational methods are used in the colleges to teach English. All the teachers do is translate everything into Telugu and refer to it as a bilingual or translational method. Even though this approach is very effective in this field and gives students solid content knowledge, it keeps them from developing the kind of English communication skills that are now expected of them. This district's students speak English like the mother tongue interference in Telugu pronunciations. Owing to the lack of natural resources, students must monitor Telugu language habits in order to generate new sounds and structures. The two languages have different patterns, and because of the students' deliberate word arrangement efforts, the translations are literal and lack grammatical structure. This district uses a grammar translation method to teach English to its undergraduate students.

What Sort Of Things Is Mother Tongue Influential For?

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As previously stated, various languages influence English studying in an alternative manner. Sentence word order can be problematic for certain people. It's possible to hear statements like "I eat toast for breakfast" or "I'm going to America tomorrow. "Usually, this can be easily fixed by reminding students of the proper word order and encouraging them to practice, practice, and more practice. In actuality, most mistakes can be corrected with just more practice. There may be issues with pronunciation in other languages. Germans saying phrases like "Welcome to my home" and pronouncing "W" as "V" are a classic example of this. One other well-known mother tongue influence is the way that French people pronounce the letter 'H'. Speakers of various languages will use a "schwa". This is the point at which they end words with a sound, saying Bird, Birdda, or Dogga instead of Dog. Usually, there are two reasons for this: first, they were given phonics instruction in error or neglected it.

Another reason for a schwa is that some languages, like Chinese, have very different phonemes and pronunciations. It can be challenging to adjust to English's sometimes softer sounds. This is also the cause of some people's difficulty pronouncing vowel sounds correctly. The influence of mother tongue cannot be entirely eliminated. Infact, some peculiarities of pronunciation from India, to lessen our pain have genuinely gained acceptance, and that is the definition of a neutral Indian accent. The goal for us Indians should be to lessen the influence of our mother tongue to the point where, instead of speaking Bengali, Tamil, Marathi, Punjabi, Bhojpuri, or Telugu, we speak Indian English.

Approaches to Teaching English:

There are numerous challenges and worries associated with teaching and learning English. The lecture method is still used for instruction in the degree colleges, bilingual and translation grammar approach. Teachers and students don't interact. Few students are brave enough to speak with English teachers in English and are able to face them. All of the colleges use the lecture method, which ends when the syllabus is finished and students leave after passing the exam. Instructors aren't searching for something inspiring and thrilling. The chalk-and-talk approach is inadequate to meet the needs of the pupils.

Students who use the grammar-translation method become reliant on their mother tongue. They translate everything they read into their native tongue. Students have either mother tongue or Telugu as their instruction language. In this instance, a teacher serves more

as a translator than as a qualified English instructor. Thus, there aren't really any differences between Telugu and English teachers.

Experimental Study Design and Findings

The experimental study aimed to investigate the influence of mother tongue instruction on the academic performance and overall well-being of tribal students at the graduation level. The study was conducted with a sample of 50 students from tribal communities, with half of the participants being instructed in their mother tongue and the other half in a second language.

To measure academic performance, both groups of students were evaluated using standardized tests in various subject areas. Additionally, qualitative data was collected through interviews and observations to gauge the students' attitudes, motivation, and emotional well-being.

The findings of the experimental study revealed the following:

The students who received instruction in their mother tongue exhibited higher academic performance compared to those taught in a second language. The mother tongue instructional group consistently scored better on standardized tests in all subject areas, demonstrating a deeper understanding of concepts and better analytical skills. Students instructed in their mother tongue displayed higher levels of motivation and engagement in the learning process. They actively participated in classroom discussions, asked questions, and expressed their opinions freely. This level of involvement positively impacted their overall academic performance and attitude towards learning. Tribal students who learned in their mother tongue experienced a greater sense of emotional well-being. They exhibited higher self-esteem, confidence, and a positive attitude towards education. Additionally, these students demonstrated stronger relationships with their teachers and peers, creating a supportive learning environment.

Implications and Recommendations

The experimental study demonstrates the significant influence of mother tongue education on the academic performance and overall well-being of tribal students at the graduation level. Based on these findings, several recommendations can be made:

- **Integration of Mother Tongue in Curriculum**

Education policymakers should consider integrating the mother tongue into the curriculum for tribal students at the graduation level. This integration can be achieved through bilingual

or multilingual instruction, teaching core subjects in the mother tongue while gradually introducing the second language.

- **Training for Teachers**

To effectively implement mother tongue instruction, teachers should receive appropriate training and professional development. This training could include pedagogical strategies, language proficiency development, and cultural sensitivity workshops. Well-equipped teachers can provide effective instruction and support learners' language and academic development.

- **Community Involvement**

Involving the tribal community in the education of their children is paramount. Community members can contribute by sharing their knowledge, resources, and cultural insights. This collaboration strengthens the connection between education and culture, leading to more inclusive and culturally relevant instruction.

Conclusion:

The experimental study highlights the significance of mother tongue instruction for tribal students at the graduation level. Utilizing the mother tongue in education enhances academic performance, cognitive and emotional development, and preserves the cultural identity of tribal students. To ensure the success of these students, it is crucial to integrate the mother tongue in the curriculum, provide necessary teacher training, and foster community involvement. By recognizing and valuing the linguistic and cultural diversity of tribal students, we can create an inclusive and empowering education system that supports their academic and personal growth.

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